

THE IMPORTANCE OF WORKING ON TEXT IN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL READING LESSONS

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Annotation: The article describes the idea that the historical progress of a personality society is growing from the simplest to a complex, multifaceted social relationship. If the simplest ties are based on the fact that seed members in the primitive community system in many cases transmit information to each other about the source of food, the risks that arise, directions for organizing actions, complex, multifaceted social relations – in the process of production, service, education, health, security, fulfillment of civil obligations (for example, payment of taxes) are visible in the organization of The correct, rational organization of social relations ensures, firstly, that the issue being resolved has a positive solution, secondly, that time is saved, and thirdly, that the process of intimate communication occurs.

Keywords: speech cultivation, work on the text, oral and written speech, communication, word meaning, speech.

In the educational sphere of each state, the cultivation of speech in children is recognized as the main structural element of the system. In Uzbekistan, the first stages of continuing education – the cultivation of speech in children during preschool and primary education-are established as an important direction of the pedagogical process. The formation of a global informatization and an innovative educational environment, an increase in the social need for the development of human capital necessitate a comprehensive maturation, intellectual development of the younger generation, the use of speech opportunities in this.

Taking into account that the stages of preschool and primary education in the cultivation of personality speech are the initial period, their improvement shows how relevant it is to “fully integrate the content of primary education, ensure the harmony of educational elements in this content”[1].

It has been proven from a psychological and biological point of view that speech is not only the process of expression of thought, the exchange of information, the use of language tools, or its derivative [2]gina, but also the basis that develops the intellectual potential of the individual. Therefore, in the younger generation, special attention is paid to the development of speech from early childhood.

Such as "speech", "growing speech", "working on the text", "growing speech by working on the text", "growing speech by working on the text in elementary reading lessons" are important supporting concepts of the research problem. Sufficient understanding of their essence allows us to find the right, rational solution to the problem when conducting research.

Theoretical analysis has shown that the concept of "speech" is given different interpretations in the existing linguistic, pedagogical, psychological and methodological literature. In particular, in the "pedagogical encyclopedic dictionary", speech is "a form of communication (communication) carried out by means of language of people, which, along with being a means of expressing thought, is the main mechanism of thinking" [3], in the "National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan" speech refers to the processes in its oral (voice) and written manifestation, that is, the process of Speech has been described by psychologists as "the process by which a person uses language for the purpose of mastering socio-historical experience and giving it to generations, or establishing interaction, or planning his actions" [4].

The following features are manifested in speech:

1) focuses on the implementation of the need to state an idea, expresses a completed topic, is drawn up on the basis of logical and grammatical rules, is divided into independent, completed, interconnected meaningful parts (it is called connected speech) [5];

2) expressed in oral and written form;

3) the development of oral and written speech takes place in a single process;

4) nevertheless, there are serious discrepancies between oral and written speech (they are discussed in detail in the next chapter of the work);

5) speech is divided into such types as dialogical and monological according to the number of participants in the dialogue;

6) dialogue is one of the most common types of oral speech, natural forms of colloquial communication, and occurs between two or more individuals;

7) oral speech, by nature, occurs more in the form of conversation;

8) the choice of language tools to express content in relation to a monologue dialogue, which is considered one of the very important forms of speech, has a somewhat traditional in the construction of speech.

Speech cultivation has always been one of the pressing issues in the history of educational development. In particular, the large-scale establishment of recitation in old schools, as well as the method of teaching tahajji, the method

of maddiya, the method of savtia is directly related to the cultivation of speech. At the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, the text books of usuli Jadid schools, "Ustodi ilk", "Sabzazor", "Adibi ilk", "Adibi soniy", "first teacher", "second teacher", "leader Salvation", "Risolai instrument savod", "recitation book", "reading book" also took a leading place. "School-based domains taught children lessons based on their methods and experiences. So, in Uzbekistan there were specific methods of teaching and they developed. This process has not gone smoothly. Some errors and omissions were also allowed. Chunonchi, in the 20s of the 20th century, very serious mistakes were made in the development of the school. In complex programs, the system of learning the native language was disrupted: grammatical, orthographic skills were not given sufficient importance. The holistic word method in teaching Savod did not correspond to the phonetic characteristics of the language, did not provide analytical-synthetic work, did not lay the groundwork for thorough, correct writing issues. Later, September 5, 1931 "on Elementary and high school", August 25, 1932 "on the regime of elementary and high school curricula" helped the school and teachers in eliminating the mistakes and shortcomings allowed as above and in developing a training system. The analytic-synthetic sound method has been revived in speed basket teaching " [6]. It seems that the problem of growing speech and teaching a standing basket on its basis has a long history. At a natural pace, he always attracted the attention of progressive-minded intellectuals.

Speech cultivation is a pedagogical process that expresses the development of fluency skills by an individual using effectively the means of artistic expression of the language in him by mastering the rules of oral and written artistic language norms: correct pronunciation, emphasis, grammar, correct use of words. In its essence, speech cultivation refers to the practical mastery of the rules of oral and written artistic language norms by a person, including a student: correct pronunciation, accent, grammar, correct use of words, the effective use of the means of artistic expression of the language, pedagogical support using methods, tools, proper orientation, taking the necessary measures in the necessary places, as well as guiding the process.

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